

Two-Way perturbative coupling of plasma-fluid interactions

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Abstract.

This contribution focuses on the modeling of ionic wind generated by a stationary corona discharge within a steady imposed external flow. The electro-drift velocity of unipolar charges in air is generally of few hundred meter per second, whereas ionic wind flow velocity is of the order of few meter per second. For this reason, the influence of fluid advection is generally neglected in this context resulting in a one-way coupling of the charges influence onto the flow, driven by Coulomb forces. Nevertheless when considering an adverse fluid velocity larger than 10 m/s, this approximation fails and a two-way coupling arises between charges' drift and fluid flow, which is more difficult to address numerically. Developing over previous asymptotic multi-scaled two-domain approach we hereby propose a new perturbative two-way coupling method based upon the non-dimensional number M_m , which is the ratio between the macroscopic electrically induced ionic wind velocity to the microscopic drift velocity of charges. This approach predicts a near-linear dependence of the current with velocity which is successfully compared with recent experimental measurements. Furthermore, it is shown and illustrated in various configuration how the electric fields lines are deformed by the external flow, leading to a significant shrinkage of collected charges region with increasing external velocity. The relevance of these findings for electro-precipitators are discussed.

Keywords: ionic wind, corona discharge, ElectroHydroDynamic (EHD), ElectroAeroDynamic (EAD), electric propulsion, multi-inception, emitter/collector systems, SDMC, finite element, drift-region model, Kaptzov hypothesis Submitted to: *J. Phys.*

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Introduction

Direct current Corona Discharge (CD) in the presence of an external flow has been studied at least since the late sixties, by S. Chapman [1] in a point-to-plane configuration showing a drastic influence of an external flow on the observed current within a strong adverse flow. The motivation for this study was a better understanding of thunderstorm events on rapidly moving metallic objects (airplanes, wind turbines, etc...) as also recently emphasized in [2]. Security issues are obviously the first concerns associated with the need for better understanding of the coupling between

an external flow and a cold plasma in high-tension sources in open air. But since the interest for CD has resurfaced in the context of electric in-atmosphere propulsion without moving parts [3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13] during the last decade, the influence of an adverse flow onto it is also a relevant and pending issue in this context. Aside from propulsive applications, ionic wind is relevant in other contexts such as electrostatic precipitators, micro-heat transfer, air remediation, where possibly important external flow are interesting to consider.

Previous works dedicated to particle dynamics in precipitators [14, 15], have shown the significant role of an external flow on ionic wind, but most studies have considered the search for optimal configurations, without taking into account the possible influence of an external flow [16, 17, 18]. Taking into account the coupled effect of an external flow has been scarcely studied. To the best of our knowledge, aside Chapman's works [1] there were only a few number of studies conducted within this area. A recent study by Grosse et al. [19] has measured a similar nearly linear current variation with the applied external flow as first discovered in [1]. Lastly, a numerical and experimental study by Guerra-Garcia et al. [2] also reported a similar observation performed within a wind-tunnel where they also measured the effects of an external flow on the current intensity. Unfortunately, their model was not able to reproduce the observed trends and measurements. Very recently Trovato et al. [20] conducted an experiment for staged periodic multi-emitters and multi-streamlined collectors configurations, and found that, in these configurations, the current followed a non-linear trend with the external flow speed, with a small quadratic trend.

Even though corona discharge or ion drift numerical modeling has already been successfully accomplished by several authors [21, 15, 22, 23, 24], to the best of our knowledge, the numerical two-way coupling between external flow and charge drift in a CD has never been successfully modeled. Recently, a numerical study by Picella et al. [25], has considered the one-way coupling of the charges onto the flow. This approximation is only valid when the adverse fluid velocity is of the order of 10 m/s, whereby the fluid advection influence is neglected, resulting in a one-way coupling of the charges onto the flow [14, 24, 26, 27]. For higher velocities, the two-way coupling between charge drift and fluid flow must be considered. Furthermore, [26, 25] led their study in the framework of the Kaptzov hypothesis, which is a simplified approach to model CD, only asymptotically valid [28]. In this work, we investigate the two-way Electro-Aero-Dynamic (EAD) coupling between a CD and an external flow taking into account the backward effect of the flow on charge's advection. The interest for considering the CD rather than a surrogate model of it —like Kaptzov hypothesis— is to evaluate how charge's are affected by the external flow, leading to a larger current injected into the drift region. Since Kaptzov hypothesis is expected to fail within a strong external flow without an additional model —having its specific parameters— to account for the flow back coupling into charge drift, the CD model avoid the need for extra-hypothesis. On the contrary, it relies on known and established governing equations and it is expected to address the non-trivial interactions and deformations of the charges' cloud nearby the emitter, which highly depends on the electrodes configuration.

Our starting point is the multi-scale asymptotic approach of Monrolin et al.[21] combined with the "one-way" coupling with the external fluid flow previously studied by [25], so that our model does not rely on the Kaptzov hypothesis which is replaced by a full CD modeling as in [21].

In section 1 a new asymptotic expansion is introduced according to a dimensionless

M_m number which represents the ratio of microscopic to macroscopic charge speeds, as detailed in governing problems given in 1.1, and their dimensionless formulation provided in 1.2. This expansion derived in 1.3 permits to find a simplified iterative two-way formulation composed of a dominant problem corresponding to the previously mentioned one-way model [21, 25] and a first order problem being the linearized dominant problem coupled with the linearized dominant fluid problem. Section 1.4 describes the numerical method which relies on the finite element discretization, stabilized to facilitate numerical convergence in hyperbolic dominant context. Section 2 compares the obtained numerical results with experimental measurements as well as illustrates the influence of the external flow field in various emitter-collector configurations.

1. Methods

In various studies [1, 2, 19, 20] experiments with external flow speed from 10 m/s to 200 m/s in wind tunnels found a linear or nearly-linear trend between current intensity and the applied external flow speed. These findings motivate a deeper theoretical understanding of these observations derived from a dimensionless formulation of the coupled CD with Navier-Stokes equations to account for such linear response.

1.1. Governing Equations

An effective fluid model of the positive direct-current corona discharge is considered as in [8, 28], but taking into account the influence of an external velocity field \mathbf{u}^* . The dimensional two-way model for an incompressible fluid reads

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \Delta^* \varphi^* = -\frac{e}{\varepsilon_0} (n_p^* - n_n^* - n_e^*) \\ \nabla^* \cdot \underbrace{[n_e^* (\mu_e \nabla^* \varphi^* + \mathbf{u}^*) - D_e \nabla^* n_e^*]}_{\mathbf{j}_e^*} = (\alpha^* - \eta^*) \|\mathbf{j}_e^*\| + S^* \\ \nabla^* \cdot [n_p^* (-\mu_p \nabla^* \varphi^* + \mathbf{u}^*) - D_p \nabla^* n_p^*] = \alpha^* \|\mathbf{j}_e^*\| + S^* \\ \nabla^* \cdot [n_n^* (\mu_n \nabla^* \varphi^* + \mathbf{u}^*) - D_n \nabla^* n_n^*] = \eta^* \|\mathbf{j}_e^*\| \\ \rho_f^* \mathbf{u}^* \cdot \nabla^* \mathbf{u}^* + \nabla^* p^* - \mu_f^* \Delta^* \mathbf{u}^* = -(n_p^* - n_e^* - n_n^*) \nabla^* \varphi^* \\ \nabla^* \cdot \mathbf{u}^* = 0, \end{array} \right. \quad (1)$$

where φ^* is the electric potential, e the electron charge, ε_0 the di-electric constant, n^* are the effective charge densities (having lower index p for positive, n for negative and e for the electrons), μ are charge's mobility (same convention for lower index), D charge diffusivities (same convention for lower index), p^* the gas pressure, μ_f^* and ρ_f^* the gas viscosity and density. Electron, positive and negative ion production in CD produced by Townsend avalanches process and being source terms on (1)'s r.h.s is governed by impact and attachment coefficient, respectively noted α^* and η^* . The ionization coefficient will depend on the electric field, following the standard Townsend form

$$\alpha^* = \beta^* e^{-E_i^*/E^*} \quad (2)$$

Plasma-Fluid Coupling

4

$B^* [m^{-2}]$	$C^* [V \cdot m^{-2}]$	$B_\eta^* [m^{-2}]$	$C_\eta^* [V \cdot m^{-2}]$	$D_\eta^* [-]$
$2,9 \cdot 10^{-20}$	$8,24 \cdot 10^{-19}$	$9,56 \cdot 10^{-23}$	$2,97 \cdot 10^{-19}$	1,65

Table 1: Fitted parameters for Townsend avalanche's attachment/detachment coefficients α & η in air at atmospheric pressure and 293K.

where β^* and E_i^* are two physical parameters dependent on the gas composition and thermodynamic conditions and E^* is the norm of the electric field. For air at atmospheric pressure conditions, the very same parameters as Monrolin et al. [21] are used

$$\frac{\alpha^*}{N} = B^* \exp\left(-\frac{C^*}{E^*/N}\right) \quad (3)$$

as for the attachment coefficient η , whose reduced form is given by

$$\frac{\eta^*}{N} = \frac{B_\eta^* \exp\left(-\frac{C_\eta^*}{E^*/N}\right)}{\left(\frac{E^*/N}{C_\eta^*}\right)^{D_\eta^*}} \quad (4)$$

where B_η^* , C_η^* and D_η^* coefficients are taken as in [21] and detailed in 2. S^* is the photo-ionization source term associated with secondary ionization, the detail of which is discussed in [21]. It is a source term for electrons and positive charges, generating both an electron and a positive charge out of a neutral molecule, hence being absent from the negative charge's conservation equation. The first equation of (1) is the Poisson problem for electrostatic potential φ^* [V]. The following three equations are the charge conservation equations respectively for electrons, positive and negative ions. These are coupled with the fluid flow from taking into account the advection flux. The source terms for the electron conservation equation is the effective ionization coefficient, which is the difference between the ionization and attachment coefficients thus achieving a balance between generated and lost electrons in Townsend avalanches, as well as including those created by photo-ionization. For the positive ion conservation flux, the source term is also composed of the ionization coefficient and photo-ionization. Photo-ionization is of prime importance in corona discharge [29, 30] since it permits the self-sustained feeding of the corona discharge, so that, even though the current characteristics of the discharge are not greatly altered by the precise input values of photo-ionization, it would not ignite without it. Finally, the only source term for the negative ion conservation fluxes is the attachment coefficient. The two last equations are the Navier-Stokes equations with a forcing external Coulomb force, together with the incompressibility condition which is valid in the considered limit of low Mach number. Boundary conditions associated with (1) are the same as in [21, 25] hence only briefly mentioned here. The electric potential fulfills Dirichlet boundary conditions on the electrodes, with a high voltage on the emitter and zero potential on the collector

$$\varphi_{|\partial\Omega_e}^* = \varphi_a^*, \quad \varphi_{|\partial\Omega_c}^* = 0 \quad (5)$$

As explained in [21], in positive corona discharge a zero positive charge flux is set at the emitter, and symmetrically alike for electrons and negative charges at collector

$$\mathbf{j}_p^* \cdot \mathbf{n}_{|\partial\Omega_e} = 0 \quad \& \quad \mathbf{j}_e^* \cdot \mathbf{n}_{|\partial\Omega_e} = 0 \quad \& \quad \mathbf{j}_n^* \cdot \mathbf{n}_{|\partial\Omega_c} = 0 \quad (6)$$

Plasma-Fluid Coupling

5

In this study the electric field at the domain's external edges is considered very low, as well as the ion densities. As for the fluid boundary conditions, a no-slip velocity at the emitter and collector surfaces is considered

$$\mathbf{u}^*_{|\partial\Omega_e} = \mathbf{0} \quad \& \quad \mathbf{u}^*_{|\partial\Omega_c} = \mathbf{0} \quad (7)$$

whereas a stress-free velocity condition is chosen over the downstream and lateral boundaries

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}^* \cdot \mathbf{n}_{|\partial\Omega_{top} \cup \partial\Omega_{bot} \cup \partial\Omega_{out}} = 0 \quad (8)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^*$ is the gas stress-tensor $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^* = -p^*\mathbf{I} + \mu_f^*(\nabla\mathbf{u}^* + \nabla\mathbf{u}^{*T})$. Finally, for the inlet boundary, we impose a constant velocity U_{in}^* and tangential stress-free conditions

$$\mathbf{u}^* \cdot \mathbf{n}_{|\partial\Omega_{in}} = U_{in}^* \quad \& \quad \mathbf{t} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}^* \cdot \mathbf{n}_{|\partial\Omega_{in}} = 0. \quad (9)$$

1.2. Dimensionless Formulation

Proceeding as in [28, 31, 21, 32], the reference applied potential is set as the one applied at the emitter φ_a^* , the reference length chosen as the collector radius r_c^* and the reference ion and electron number density N_k^* , as in [33]

$$N_k^* = \frac{\varepsilon_0 \varphi_a^* \mu_p}{e r_c^{*2} \mu_k},$$

where $k = e, p, n$, for electrons, positive and negative ions. As for the dimensionless fluid variables, the reference speed is chosen as the ionic wind velocity U_e^* resulting from the balance between Coulomb force and inertia

$$U_e^* = \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon_0 \varphi_a^*}{\rho_f^* r_c^*}} \quad (10)$$

and the reference pressure is set as the resulting ionic-wind's Bernoulli pressure $p^* = \rho_f^* U_e^{*2}$. Finally, as in [8], a small asymptotic parameter ε compares the applied "external" field to the "internal" one associated with the electric ionization field of Townsend avalanches

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\varphi_a^*}{r_c^* E_i^*} \quad (11)$$

In [21] an asymptotic expansion based on ε is formulated separating the physical domain into two distinct ones, each having its specific modeling. Dimensionless parameters are then given by

$$\mathbf{r} = \frac{\mathbf{r}^*}{r_c^*}, \quad \varphi = \frac{\varphi^*}{\varphi_a^*}, \quad n_k = \frac{n_k^*}{\frac{\varepsilon_0 \varphi_a^* \mu_p}{e r_c^{*2} \mu_k}} \equiv \frac{n_k^*}{N_k^*}, \quad \mathbf{u} = \frac{\mathbf{u}^*}{U_e^*}, \quad p = \frac{p^*}{\rho_f^* U_e^{*2}} \quad (12)$$

Using (12), the dimensionless version of (1) reads

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \Delta\varphi = -(n_p - \delta_{\mu_n} n_n - \delta_{\mu_e} n_e) \\ \nabla \cdot [n_e(\nabla\varphi + \delta_{\mu_e} M_m \mathbf{u}) - \frac{\delta_{\mu_e}}{P_e} \nabla n_e] = (\alpha - \eta) \|\mathbf{j}_e\| + \gamma S \\ \nabla \cdot [n_p(-\nabla\varphi + M_m \mathbf{u}) - \frac{1}{P_e} \nabla n_p] = \alpha \|\mathbf{j}_e\| + \delta_{\mu_e} \gamma S \\ \nabla \cdot [n_n(\nabla\varphi + M_m \mathbf{u}) - \frac{\delta_{\mu_n}}{P_e} \nabla n_n] = \eta \|\mathbf{j}_e\| \\ \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla p - \frac{1}{R_e} \Delta \mathbf{u} = -(n_p - \delta_{\mu_n} n_n - \delta_{\mu_e} n_e) \nabla \varphi \\ \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0, \end{array} \right. \quad (13)$$

where the dimensionless parameters are the electrical Peclet number

$$P_e = \frac{\mu_p \varphi_a^*}{D_\rho}, \quad (14)$$

being large, i.e. $P_e \sim 10^4$, an electric macroscopic to microscopic speed ratio number denoted M_m

$$M_m = \frac{U_e^*}{\mu_p \varphi_a^* / r_c^*} = \frac{1}{\mu_p} \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon_0}{\rho_f^*}}, \quad (15)$$

which is small, i.e. $M_m \sim 10^{-2}$, the mobility ratio

$$\delta_{\mu_e} = \frac{\mu_p}{\mu_e} \quad \delta_{\mu_n} = \frac{\mu_p}{\mu_n}, \quad (16)$$

having distinct order of magnitude, i.e. $\delta_{\mu_n} \sim O(1)$ but $\delta_{\mu_e} \sim 10^{-2}$. In the following, since the precise value of δ_{μ_n} is not easy to find from literature data, it is set as $\delta_{\mu_n} = 1$. This issue is mild since, for the considered high Péclet limit, the diffusive term is almost negligible. Furthermore, since in the Poisson equation, as well as in the Coulomb forcing of Navier-Stokes equations, the contribution of negative charges in the corona discharge is extremely small, the model is almost insensitive to a $\delta_{\mu_n} \sim O(1)$ variations. Note also, that with the chosen dimensionless formulation there is no Masuda number in front of the dimensionless Coulomb force in the Navier-Stokes equation on the contrary to [26] (the choice for the reference velocity (10) is equivalent to set a Masuda number equal to one). Notations for each boundary are illustrated in fig 1. Following (5)-(9) dimensionless boundary conditions reads

$$\varphi|_{\partial\Omega_e} = 1 \quad \& \quad \varphi|_{\partial\Omega_c} = 0 \quad (17)$$

$$\mathbf{j}_p \cdot \mathbf{n}|_{\partial\Omega_e} = 0 \quad \& \quad \mathbf{j}_e \cdot \mathbf{n}|_{\partial\Omega_c} = 0 \quad \& \quad \mathbf{j}_n \cdot \mathbf{n}|_{\partial\Omega_c} = 0 \quad (18)$$

$$\mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{n}|_{\partial\Omega_{in} \cup \partial\Omega_{out} \cup \partial\Omega_{top} \cup \partial\Omega_{bot}} = 0 \quad \& \quad \mathbf{j}_p \cdot \mathbf{n}|_{\partial\Omega_{in} \cup \partial\Omega_{out} \cup \partial\Omega_{top} \cup \partial\Omega_{bot}} = 0 \quad (19)$$

$$\mathbf{u}|_{\partial\Omega_e} = \mathbf{0} \quad \& \quad \mathbf{u}|_{\partial\Omega_c} = \mathbf{0} \quad (20)$$

$$\sigma \cdot \mathbf{n}|_{\partial\Omega_{top} \cup \partial\Omega_{bot} \cup \partial\Omega_{out}} = \mathbf{0} \quad (21)$$

Plasma-Fluid Coupling

7

with σ the dimensionless stress-tensor. Finally, for the inlet boundary

$$\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n}|_{\partial\Omega_{in}} = \frac{U_{in}^*}{U_e^*} \equiv \beta \quad \& \quad \mathbf{t} \cdot \sigma \cdot \mathbf{n}|_{\partial\Omega_{in}} = 0, \quad (22)$$

a dimensionless inlet velocity β has been introduced together with the tangential stress-free conditions. In the following β is obviously not considered as a small parameter but treated as being $O(1)$. Note that the product $\beta M_m = M_c^e$ is the same as [25].

1.3. Asymptotic expansion in M_m

The dimensionless problem solution is then searched within a regular expansion

$$X = X^0 + M_m X^1 + O(M_m^2) \quad (23)$$

for each variable $X \equiv [\varphi, n_p, n_n, n_e, \mathbf{u}, p]$. The leading order reads

$$\begin{cases} \Delta\varphi^0 = -(n_p^0 - n_n^0 - \delta_{\mu_e} n_e^0) \\ \nabla \cdot [n_e^0 \nabla\varphi^0 - \frac{\delta_{\mu_e}}{P_e} \nabla n_e^0] = (\alpha - \eta) \|n_e^0 \nabla\varphi^0 - \frac{1}{P_e} \nabla n_e^0\| + S^0 \\ \nabla \cdot [-n_p^0 \nabla\varphi^0 - \frac{1}{P_e} \nabla n_p^0] = \alpha \|n_e^0 \nabla\varphi^0 - \frac{1}{P_e} \nabla n_e^0\| + S^0 \\ \nabla \cdot [n_n^0 \nabla\varphi^0 - \frac{1}{P_e} \nabla n_n^0] = \eta \|n_e^0 \nabla\varphi^0 - \frac{1}{P_e} \nabla n_e^0\| \end{cases} \quad (24)$$

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{u}^0 \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u}^0 + \nabla p^0 - \frac{1}{R_e} \Delta \mathbf{u}^0 = -(n_p^0 - \delta_{\mu_e} n_e^0 - n_n^0) \nabla \varphi^0 \\ \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}^0 = 0 \end{cases} \quad (25)$$

(24) and (25) is exactly similar with the "one-way" coupling problem examined in many papers e.g.[34, 25] where the electrical problem is independent from the fluid one, whereas, on the contrary the fluid dynamic is enforced by the Coulomb force. The one-way coupling approximation, seems to be accurate with experimental measurements up to 50 m/s in [2, 19] or even 110 m/s in [1]. (24) and (25) are thus consistent with previous approaches since the leading order electrical problem is the same as in [21] as for the fluid [34, 26, 25] but for a distinct choice for the velocity reference length-scale, which is arbitrary. This choice nevertheless turns out to be a key point to establish that the "one-way" coupling problem is the leading order asymptotic model of the full two-way coupling one. Two-way coupling involves the fluid back-coupling onto the

ion drift fluxes, arising at first order

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \Delta\varphi^1 = -(n_p^1 - n_n^1 - \delta_{\mu_e} n_e^1) \\ \nabla \cdot [n_e^1 \nabla\varphi^0 + n_e^0 \nabla\varphi^1 - \frac{\delta_{\mu_e}}{P_e} \nabla n_e^1] = \\ \quad (\alpha - \eta) \|n_e^0 \nabla\varphi^1 + n_e^1 \nabla\varphi^0 - \frac{\delta_{\mu_e}}{P_e} \nabla n_e^1\| + \gamma S^1 - \nabla \cdot (n_e^0 \mathbf{u}^0) \\ \nabla \cdot [-n_p^1 \nabla\varphi^0 - n_p^0 \nabla\varphi^1 - \frac{1}{P_e} \nabla n_p^1] = \\ \quad \alpha \|n_e^0 \nabla\varphi^1 + n_e^1 \nabla\varphi^0 - \frac{\delta_{\mu_e}}{P_e} \nabla n_e^1\| + \gamma S^1 - \nabla \cdot (n_p^0 \mathbf{u}^0) \\ \nabla \cdot [n_n^1 \nabla\varphi^0 + n_n^0 \nabla\varphi^1 - \frac{1}{P_e} \nabla n_n^1] = \\ \quad \eta \|n_e^0 \nabla\varphi^1 + n_e^1 \nabla\varphi^0 - \frac{\delta_{\mu_e}}{P_e} \nabla n_e^1\| - \nabla \cdot (n_n^0 \mathbf{u}^0) \end{array} \right. \quad (26)$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathbf{u}^0 \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u}^1 + \mathbf{u}^1 \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u}^0 + \nabla p^1 - \frac{1}{Re} \Delta \mathbf{u}^1 = -(n_p^1 - \delta_{\mu_e} n_e^1 - n_n^1) \nabla \varphi^0 - (n_p^0 - \delta_{\mu_e} n_e^0 - n_n^0) \nabla \varphi^1 \\ \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}^1 = 0 \end{array} \right. \quad (27)$$

(26)-(27) is also a one-way problem, but differs from (24) and (25) by being linear but driven by the leading order charge advection source terms, i.e $-\nabla \cdot (n_e^0 \mathbf{u}^0)$, $-\nabla \cdot (n_p^0 \mathbf{u}^0)$, $-\nabla \cdot (n_n^0 \mathbf{u}^0)$ ensuring the fluid's back-coupling into ion drift fluxes. This approach also provides a hierarchy of problems for tackling the two-way coupling which only adds two supplementary steps to previous one-way coupling (as in [25] for example) i.e (i) leading order drift-diffusion involving electrostatic problem and charge densities fluxes (ii) leading order Navier-Stokes equations forced by leading order Coulomb term. To this, (26)-(27) adds (iii) first order linear electrostatic problem forced by leading order electrostatic and Navier-Stokes equations (iv) first order linearized Navier-Stokes equations forced by first order electric problem. As the leading order electrostatic problem is exactly the same as [21], it is solved alike, with a two-domain approach not repeated here but given in appendix : an inner region denoted Ω_1 associated with the corona discharge modeling where Townsend avalanche process occurs and an outer region denoted Ω_2 where drift-diffusion arises.

1.4. Numerical Methods

Finite Element Methods (FEM) implemented with software FreeFem++ [35] monitored and post-processed with the Stabfem interface [36] are hereby used.

The numerical implementation of the leading order electrical problem (A.1)-(A.5), being the same as in [21] will not be detailed. A SUPG/PSPG-stabilized variational formulation of the outer region Ω_2 leading order equations (A.1)-(A.5), and matching conditions (A.21), (A.31), (A.33) are implemented via the addition of Lagrangian multipliers to the formulation of the problem, as described by [37], or for more details [38]. The weak formulation is detailed in the following section, but with lightened notations omitting the usual subscript h associated with fields defined in the finite element discrete functional space.

1.4.1. Practical details concerning the simulation of the Navier-Stokes equations The reader may have noticed that the previous discussion doesn't distinguish between the inner Ω_1 and the outer domain Ω_2 of the two-domain approach used to solve the fluid problems (25) and (27). This was on purpose since only the positive and negative ions are taken into account in the modeling of the flow, as electrons are only considered within the ionization region Ω_1 since their collisions with neutral air particles are negligible in Ω_2 whilst also of negligible influence on the external flow. So do negative ions as they also have a negligible impact both in Ω_1 & Ω_2 .

To lighten the paper's reading the two-domain strong and the weak formulations sets of equations are given in Appendix A. Equations (A.1) to (A.8) detail the leading order two-domain strong formulation, the first order equations then being given by equations (A.10) to (A.17), and the boundary conditions given by (A.19) to (A.39). The electric problem (A.1)-(A.5) is solved within a monolithic two-domains Ω_1 & Ω_2 approach using the weak formulation detailed in [21] and the first order in (A.40), whilst, on the contrary, the fluid one (A.8) is defined within the single merged domain $\Omega = \Omega_1 \cup \Omega_2$, so that one needs to connect the field's solutions from one-another, e.g the velocity fields components are decomposed as $\mathbf{u}_\Omega = \mathbf{u}_{\Omega_1} \mathbb{1}_{\Omega_1} + \mathbf{u}_{\Omega_2} \mathbb{1}_{\Omega_2}$, where domain indicator function $\mathbb{1}_A(\mathbf{r}) = 1$ if $\mathbf{r} \in A$ and 0 elsewhere. Once the solution of the leading order Navier-Stokes problem has been solved, it is interpolated into the inner Ω_1 and outer Ω_2 in order to solve the first order electric problem (A.10)-(A.14). To solve the first order fluid problem (A.17) the same procedure is applied to solve the leading order one. The computations are performed via a continuation method combined with an automatic mesh refinement procedure along the path of dimensionless control parameters (Pe , Re , β). This procedure is most often first performed on the Reynolds number Re , and secondly on the inlet flow speed β . The stepping choice of the continuation method as well as the mesh refinement are generally crucial to reach convergence.

2. Results

2.1. Comparison with experimental measurements

To our knowledge, the only experiments measuring current intensity when varying the external flow speed in a 2D-reproducible configuration were the recent works by Grosse et al.[19] and by Guerra-Garcia et al.[2]. Note that Chapman's results [1] being obtained within a point-to-plane configuration (not a wire-to-plane) can not be investigated with a 2D computation but necessitate a 3D one for quantitative comparison.

The studied configurations are depicted in figure 1. Grosse et al. [19] have studied two distinct configurations : a one wire-to-cylinder (Cf figure 1a) and one wire-to-NACA0012 (Cf figure 1b). Here are the most salient features regarding both meshing of experimental configurations. The collecting cylinder has radius $r_c^* = 3\text{mm}$ whilst the NACA0012's chord is $l_c = 5\text{cm}$, and a maximum thickness $2r_c^* = 6\text{mm}$. [19] used a wind tunnel with square test section of $X_m = Y_m = 456\text{mm}$ span. The free-stream velocity was chosen from 3 to 50 m/s. In both configurations, the emitter radius has been $50\mu\text{m}$ and the emitter-collector face-to-face distance $d = 4\text{ cm}$. It is important to mention that this face-to-face distance can not be perfectly controlled experimentally and varies with the external flow drag since the emitter's wire is flexible even if fixed at both sides of the test section, it remains free to deform or move. More precisely, as the

Figure 1: Sketch of the various considered configurations. (a) A wire-to-cylindrical collector from Grosse et al. [19]; (b) A wire-to-NACA0012 collector from Grosse et al. [19]; (c) Gerra-Garcia et al.[2] configuration ; (d) A wire-to-two NACA0012 configuration.

external flow speed increases, the emitter wire bends to a parabolic shape. As a result the average face-to-face distance varies from 1% at 30m/s to almost 10% at 50 m/s, as reported in [19]. This effect has been taken into consideration, by adapting the face-to-face distance to the corresponding average experimental face-to-face distance at a given external flow speed up until 20 m/s, then 30 m/s, and lastly at 50 m/s. Simulations have managed to reach external speeds of about 50 m/s. Additional predictions can nevertheless be obtained, from extrapolating the asymptotic linear trend versus U_{in}^* from low velocity range. Numerical simulations are confronted with experimental ones using dimensional current intensity computed as

$$I^* = \int_{\partial\Omega_c} \mu_p n_p^* \frac{\varphi_a^*}{r_c^*} (n_p^0 E^0 + M_m (n_p^0 E^1 + n_p^1 E^0)) \quad (28)$$

Rather than (28) the current intensity can also be evaluated from integrating along the emitter surface $\partial\Omega_e$, both differing by less than two percent with the chosen meshes.

Figure 2: Experimental measurements (triangular dots) compared with numerical predictions (solid line). (a) [19]’s wire-to-cylinder configuration with cylinder radius $r_c = 3\text{mm}$, emitter radius $r_e = 50\mu\text{m}$, emitter-collector face-to-face distance $d = 4\text{cm}$ (b) [19]’s wire-to-NACA0012 configuration with NACA0012’s chord $l_c = 5\text{cm}$, and maximum thickness $2r_c = 6\text{mm}$, emitter radius $r_e = 50\mu\text{m}$, emitter-collector face-to-face distance $d = 4\text{cm}$. (c) [2]’s configuration with collector length $l_c = 14\text{cm}$, width $r_c = 1\text{cm}$ and face-to-face distance $d = 4\text{cm}$.

ρ_f^* [$kg \cdot m^{-3}$]	μ_f^* [$kg \cdot m^{-1} \cdot s^{-1}$]	μ [$m^2/V \cdot s$]	γ
1.225	$1,5 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$2 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2 \cdot 10^{-3}$

Table 2: Table with the physical parameters of the simulations

Confrontation with experimental measurements has been performed without any parameter adjustments, sticking to provided experimental parameters and known ones (Cf Tab 2) and [21]. Concerning Grosse et al.'s [19], numerical predictions have been adapted to the provided emitter flexion reported in [19] so that the face-to-face emitter/collector distance d is accordingly shortened as U_{in}^* increases, leading to a slightly non-linear trend of the continuous predictions between current intensity and inlet velocity U_{in}^* in Figure 2, albeit the asymptotic two-way solution is mainly linear in U_{in}^* . These predictions favorably compare with the experimental points of [19], within a 0-24% after $U_{in}^* = 20$ m/s albeit, in the wire-to-cylinder case, at low external speed and for highest tensions, where the current intensity is overestimated by almost 40% in figure 2a. Since, at zero external speed the corona discharge model has already been successfully validated in [21], this discrepancy might be attributed to additional effects not taken into account such as —possibly— partial back-discharge. Also, it is interesting to note that, for most of Figure 2a-b curves, removing the initial discrepancy between the predicted current and the experimental measurement at zero external velocity would lead to a very precise prediction of the velocity influence. This suggests that two-way coupling effects are accurately captured in these cases. The comparison with Guerra-Garcia's data depicted in figure 2c, first shows that at zero external velocity, the numerical prediction underestimates the current intensity by 30%. This poor estimation in the absence of forced convection is somehow similar with Guerra-Garcia's inability to numerically match with their experimental results in [2], but for a much smaller discrepancy in our case. Also, the observed slightly non-linear trend of the experimental points of figure 2c might partly result from the emitter wire bending (as in [19]) but is not documented in [2], hence not corrected in the numerical predictions (continuous curve), being, as a result, linear. Estimating the slope of the experimental data with a linear fit shows that the current intensity prediction overestimates the experimental trend by about 33%. Even though the dynamics of the coupling are accurately captured by the numerical model at high applied voltages, it presents larger errors at smaller applied potentials. Comparing minimal and maximal errors in the figure 3 leads to two comments. First, the errors between predictions and experiments decrease with the applied potential. This may indicate that the approach might not entirely capture the full coupling resulting in an approximate ignition voltage prediction modifications with external flow speed. Nevertheless ignition voltage modifications were measured by Trovato et al. [20], leading consequently to large errors at smaller applied potentials. In fact, at 16kV of applied potential for the NACA0012 configuration from Grosse et al. [19], the error ranges from about 29.5% to 36.4%, whereas at 28kV it levels-down to about 2.7% to 7.5%. Interestingly enough, error seems to decrease near-linearly with the applied potential. Secondly, errors are not constant across all velocity ranges, but rather vary about 5% at all applied potentials.

Finally it is interesting to confront the thrust generated by Grosse et al.'s configurations, with their experimental measurements, where they found an almost constant EHD thrust, close to 60mN/m. The thrust is estimated from a fluid domain

Figure 3: Minimal errors (dashed lines) and maximal errors (continuous lines) of the current intensity of Grosse et al.'s [19] cylindrical collector (blue) and NACA0012 collector (red) configurations for all applied potentials

integration of the Coulomb forcing

$$T_{EHD}^* = \int_{\Omega} n_p^{*0} E^{*0} + M_m (n_p^{*0} E^{*1} + n_p^{*1} E^{*0}) \quad (29)$$

The EHD thrust definition (29) relying on a fluid domain integration can equivalently be formulated within an edge-domain integration definition involving Maxwell's tensor projection onto the local normal [8], the later being less than 1 % different. The total thrust generated by the wire-to-NACA0012 at a 24kV applied potential and the wire-to-cylinder at 28kV is thus estimated and compared with the Grosse et al.'s measurements [19] against the external speed in figure 4. Grosse et al. investigate the aerodynamic forces by momentum conservation balance from inlet/outlet velocity profile measurements. In the absence of applied voltage, the drag has been estimated from known C_D coefficient ($C_D = 0.025$ in their configuration), and usual quadratic law using the inlet velocity. The EHD Thrust was found from subtracting the two measurements with and without applied voltage. To check if the numerical thrust correctly predicts Grosse et al.'s measurements, we estimate the thrust by computing the EHD thrust and then subtracting Grosse et al.'s measured drag. Fig. 4 displays the thrust computed with the experimentally measured thrust by Grosse et al. in two distinct configurations : NACA0012 collector at 24kV of applied voltage and cylindrical collector at 28kV applied voltage, the computed results seem to show a very good agreement with the experimentally measured thrust.

Figure 4: Comparison between Grosse et al.'s experimentally measured thrust (dots) and the thrust computed by subtracting the numerically computed EHD Thrust (cf. (29)) from the experimental drag in the absence of a discharge (solid lines) for two different configurations : a NACA0012 collector at 24kV of applied voltage (blue line) and cylindrical collector at 28kV applied voltage (red line)

It is necessary to mention that Trovato et al.'s [20] test case has not been investigated in this contribution because it involves a large number of emitter's which are not easy to deal with within the considered multi-domain formulation, needing as much numerical fields and meshes as emitters.

2.2. Effects of external flow speed on the Corona Discharge

Figure 5 represents the ion density charge distribution with the same iso-contours for each configuration, for distinct inlet flow speeds, from left to right: $U_{in}^* = 1$ m/s, $U_{in}^* = 24$ m/s and $U_{in}^* = 49.1$ m/s for configuration (a), and (b), and $U_{in}^* = 1$ m/s, $U_{in}^* = 5.7$ m/s and $U_{in}^* = 12.3$ m/s for panel (c). From top to bottom, the considered configurations are the wire-to-cylinder configuration and wire-to-NACA0012 from [19], and wire to two NACA0012 reported in Figure 1d. The iso-contours are the same within each configuration. The color gradient and iso-contours indicate an increase of ion charge density with inlet flow speed level-up. One can observe in figure 5 the iso-contour are enlarged and shifted toward the collector as the external flow speed rises. Furthermore the iso-contour profiles do not show much difference between the cylindrical collector —Figure 5a— and the single NACA0012 one —Figure 5b—. However, their profile clearly differs when two NACA0012 collectors are considered in figure 5c, where one can observe that the represented iso-contour first connects to the NACA collectors for $U_{in}^* = 5.7$ m/s, as well as is shifted along it for $U_{in}^* = 12.3$ m/s with a charge accumulation layer at collector's back.

Figure 5 shows that the external flow speed increases both ion density and ion generation, a physical explanation for this is now provided. The electric dimensionless model (13) is rewritten in terms of charge fluxes to better understand the effect of charge advection on ion generation.

Figure 5: Ion density and iso-contours for three different configurations at three different external velocities U_{in}^* , respectively from left to right: $U_{in}^* = 1$ m/s, $U_{in}^* = 24$ m/s and $U_{in}^* = 49.1$ m/s for configuration (a) and (b), and respectively from left to right: $U_{in}^* = 1$ m/s, $U_{in}^* = 5.7$ m/s and $U_{in}^* = 12.3$ m/s for configurations (c). From top to bottom the configurations are (a) wire-to-cylinder configuration (Cf Figure fig:configa) from [19], (b) wire-to-NACA0012 (Cf Figure 1b) also from [19], and (c) wire-to- two NACA0012 (Cf Figure 1) configuration. The iso-contours values are the same for each configurations.

$$\begin{cases} \Delta\varphi = \delta_{\mu_n} n_n + \delta_{\mu_e} n_e - n_p \\ \nabla \cdot [\mathbf{j}_p + M_m \mathbf{j}_p^{adv}] = \alpha \|\mathbf{j}_e\| + \delta_{\mu_e} \gamma S \\ \nabla \cdot [\mathbf{j}_e + \delta_{\mu_e} M_m \mathbf{j}_e^{adv}] = (\alpha - \eta) \|\mathbf{j}_e\| + \gamma S \\ \nabla \cdot [\mathbf{j}_n + \delta_{\mu_n} M_m \mathbf{j}_n^{adv}] = \eta \|\mathbf{j}_e\| \end{cases} \quad (30)$$

Where, $\mathbf{j}_k = \text{sgn}(k) n_k \mathbf{E} - \frac{\delta_{\mu_k}}{P_e} \nabla n_k$, and $\mathbf{j}_k^{adv} = n_k \mathbf{u}$ where $k = e, n, p$. Note, that electron advection's contribution to charge density increase can be neglected, from the aforementioned $\delta_{\mu_e} \sim 10^{-2}$ correction associated with it. This is due to electron's higher mobilities (electrons are smaller and faster than other ions), making them less affected by macroscopic advection phenomena, remaining always closely confined to the emitter. System (30) shows that the main mechanisms for charge creation in the ionization region are related to the standard Townsend laws α for electron avalanches and η for emission by attachment. α and η depend only on the electric field magnitude, meaning that for fluid charge advection to enhance charge creation it must modify the electric field near the emitter. An overall increase of the electric field in the ionization region by charge advection is thus responsible for the increase of charge generation. Furthermore a small enhancement of the electric field in the ionization region can lead to large charge production due to the exponential nature of the Townsend law. In fact, expanding on the standard Townsend law at first order confirms a linear increase of the charge production rate as illustrated in figure 6.

Figure 6: Charge production by electron avalanche (red curve) and electron attachment (blue dashed dot) increase with external flow speed over the whole domain

The electric field in the ionization region is modified as a consequence of the electric field's change in the drift region due to charge advection, that modification results from electric field continuity between drift and ionization regions. Hence this is a non-local Poisson's electrostatic effect. It is indeed non local because asymptotically charges have locally no effect on the electric field in the ionization region but, on the contrary, they are coupled to it in the drift region as found in (A.1) & (A.10) and

Figure 7: Close-up of the Electric field magnitude isocontours around the emitter at 0th $\|\nabla\varphi^0\|$ (left panel) and 1st order $\frac{\nabla\varphi^0 \cdot \nabla\varphi^1}{\|\nabla\varphi^0\|}$ (right panel). The velocity field streamlines associated with positive ion advection \mathbf{j}_p^{adv} of (30) are depicted with red lines with arrows for a $12m/s$ imposed external flow for NACA0012 configuration.

(A.5) & (A.14) and (A.21). Figure 7 illustrates this effect from plotting the electric field magnitude at leading order, $E^0 = \|\nabla\varphi^0\|$ i.e. in the absence of an external flow and its first order correction $E^1 = \nabla\varphi^0 \cdot \nabla\varphi^1 / \|\nabla\varphi^0\|$ modified by charge advection from the external flow, as well as the \mathbf{j}_p^{adv} field lines, around the emitter, which is essentially the same as the fluid streamlines (in red). Electric field magnitude in the absence of an external flow near the emitter (Figure 7's left panel) is isotropic. The first order correction by the fluid advection (right panel) shows a bipolar form. Notice on the right panel that the regions of enhanced electric field norm are located at the left side of the emitter, precisely where the charges are advected, as the flow speed slows down due to adherence to emitter's surface so that charges accumulate at the emitter's left side. Whereas at the right side of the emitter the opposite arises: charges are driven away from the emitter mainly by electro-drift but also from wake's advection in a region where the electric field locally decreases. Note that, as the right panel is only a corrective term, the negative electric field doesn't imply null or negative charge creation, but only smaller charge creation. Regions of enhanced electric field are regions of enhanced charge generation. Note also that with external flow speed positive ion density is larger upstream as clearly visible in figure 11, reinforcing the relation between charge creation due to fluid advection and electric field modification leading to subsequent charge generation.

Furthermore, on the one side, the ion density profile is affected by the number of collecting electrodes, so that the iso-lines stretch between both collectors, as expected. On the other side however, one can observe this unexpected ion layer forming an arch shape from one collector edge to the other. Looking only at the ion distributions is not enough to explain this layer, but a closer look at the electric potential gives a clue about its origin.

Figure 8: Electric potential and field line on the left, and ion density and electric field lines on the right, for the wire-to-2NACA0012 configuration at 16kV applied voltage for three different external flow speed, respectively from top to bottom : $U_{in}^* = 1$ m/s, $U_{in}^* = 2.87$ m/s, $U_{in}^* = 5.73$ m/s and $U_{in}^* = 12.26$ m/s. The red lines separate the collector electric attraction basin defined as the frontier where field lines are connected to collectors from those which are not, thus representing the charge collection zone. The blue dots indicates fixed points, where the electric field zeros. There is only one such point at $U_{in}^* = 1$ m/s—top panel (a.1-a.2)—but two for $U_{in}^* = 2.87$ m/s, $U_{in}^* = 5.73$ m/s and $U_{in}^* = 12.26$ m/s—panels (b.1-b.2) and (c.1-c.2)—and bottom panels (d.1-d.2) —.

Figures 8, 9 and 10 display the electric potential and field lines on the left, and ion density and electric field lines on the right, for the three previously considered configurations, i.e wire to two NACA0012, wire to cylinder and wire to NACA0012, at 24kV applied voltage for three distinct external flow speed.

Focusing first on Figure 8 top panel (a.1-a.2), a closer look nearby the collectors' back it is possible to notice a close region where the electric field becomes zero nearby the central blue dot. As external flow speed increases, the electric field lines are shifted so as to create a basin of attraction, delimited by red lines in panels (b.1-b.2), (c.1-c.2) and (d.1-d.2). For $U_{in}^* = 29$ m/s, panels (c.1-c.2), two stagnation points where the electric field zeros depicted with blue dots are visible. As the velocity increases, this basin of attraction shortens, so that the two electric field stagnation points are brought closer, until they merge (cf. blue dots in the Figure 8's panels (c.1-c.2)). The merging of these points then result in new top-bottom symmetric electric field stagnation points, also represented by blue dots in panels (d.1-d.2). From the configuration top-bottom symmetry, the electric field lines keeps changing their sign when crossing the central horizontal axis as the external flow field increases. Since the flow field is predominantly directed along the longitudinal direction nearby the central horizontal axis, the transverse collection of the charges within the charge density accumulation arc is obviously due to the transverse electric field. Thus ions accumulates in a region where the transverse electric field direction change sign, being upward above the central axis, and downward bellow it. Furthermore, the backward sharp variations of this thin ion layer being zero at a very small distance downstream the arch suggests a boundary layer — plasma's sheath— is formed from the opposed and combined effects of dominant transverse electro-convection and dominant longitudinal flow advection. Figure 8b,c, also display the attraction basin of charge collection from the electric field for increasing external velocity fields — red lines around the elongated collector shape— showing that, the size of the collected region shrinks, as well as deforms. This decreased size of field lines connected to collectors collecting the charges suggests that as the external velocity is increased, more and more charges are lost away by the advective flow. This is confirmed by a small but increasing downstream leakage electric current at the outlet frontier of the domain, as U_{in}^* rises (not shown). It is also interesting to note that this collected charge region is in fact composed of two symmetrical lobes, resulting from the top-bottom symmetry of the configuration.

Plasma-Fluid Coupling

21

Figure 9: Electric potential and field line on the left, and ion density and electric field lines on the right, for the wire-to-NACA0012 configuration at 16kV applied voltage for four different external flow speed, respectively from top to bottom : $U_{in}^* = 1$ m/s, $U_{in}^* = 24$ m/s and $U_{in}^* = 49.1$ m/s.

Plasma-Fluid Coupling

22

Figure 10: Same conventions as Figure 10 for the wire-to-NACA configuration depicted in figure 1b.

The shrinking of the collected charge region — red lines connecting the collector— is also clearly visible for the case of a single NACA collector as shown in figure 9, but having a single lobe in this more simple configuration. On this symmetrical case, the electric field stagnation point move further upstream, closer and closer to the collector's back along the horizontal axis as the external velocity increases — Cf figure 9b,c,d—. The observed decrease of the collected charge region might contradict the fact that the current intensity increases with the external flow speed, for a smaller collected region could result in less collected charges. However, one should bear in mind that albeit smaller in size, this region experiences a stronger electric field, and concomitantly, larger charge densities resulting from the increased external flow speed extraction from corona region. These two conjugate effects explains the collected current intensity increase with external flow speed.

As for the ion charge density, the influence of the external flow effect is more visible nearby the emitter where one can observe a slight downstream move of the electric potential iso-contour in the middle and bottom panels of figure 9 as speed rises. Nevertheless the advective effects on the electrical field is also visible around the collector on the electric-field line distributions depicted in the right panels of figure 9 where one can clearly see the deformation of the field lines.

Similar qualitative comments concerning both the external velocity influence on the corona discharge region as well as collected charge one can be raised in the wire-to-cylinder depicted in figure 10.

2.3. Impact of negative ions

Guided by the results of Monrollin & Plouraboué [21] the impact of negative ions is first investigated, so as to assess if they indeed are of negligible influence. Hence, computations where the last equations of (24) and (27) are taken into consideration and compared with the same configuration where they are, on the contrary, discarded.

First, considering all possible charges (positive, negative and electrons) figure 11 displays the charge density profiles around the emitter and the effect of the external flow speed on those densities. In the chosen semi-log representation it is possible to observe that both negative charge and electron dimensional densities are two orders of magnitude smaller than positive ions one's within CD. Furthermore, charge distribution are left-right asymmetrical since the collecting electrode named collector is located at emitter's right in the absence of external flow (left panels) and vice-versa in the presence of external flow (right panels). The switch of asymmetry is a direct consequence of the electric field enhancement at the leading edge of the emitter in figure 7. Also, the negative charge density very strongly decays to zero further away from the emitter, at null external flow speed, as expected from the Townsend avalanche mechanism related to attachment coefficient being non-zero only in the CD, but rapidly nullifies outside it. An imposed external flow speed increases the positive charge density in the drift region, as well as accentuates the asymmetry around the emitter for all densities (Cf horizontal dotted-dashed line for positive charge profile). Second, the total current computed when using all possible charges has been compared with the one obtained considering positive charges and electrons only in several configurations. A maximal 0.2% relative difference has been obtained accounting for the effect of negative charges in the absence of an external flow. This small effect is however no longer true in the presence of an external flow since an increase of about 13% of

Figure 11: Radial charge density profiles around the emitter in semi-log scale in a one emitter/one cylindrical collector configuration (the collector being situated far-right in this configuration, hence not visible). Dimensionless charge densities of positive (red) & negative (green) ions as well as electrons (blue) in the absence (left) and presence (right) of an external flow speed are represented. The dashed black line represents the maximum value of the density of positive ions. Top panels are dimensionless whereas bottom panels are dimensional.

current intensity slope versus the external flow speed when taking into account the negative ions is found as can be seen in figure 12. This is caused by the electric field enhancement resulting from charge advection increasing charges coming from two-way coupling. This is why the effect of negative charges has been taken into account in the results that follow.

Thirdly, the electric field within the corona discharge satisfies the Poisson equation with no source term (cf. (A.1)). Being harmonic, the electric potential produces an electric field inversely proportional to the radial distance, as expected.

Figure 12: Comparison of current intensities computed when neglecting negative ions (blue curve) and considering them (red curve) for the two NACA0012 collector configuration.

2.4. Impact on Breakdown Voltage

This section investigates a possible explanation for Trovato et al.'s [20] observation of a linear increase of breakdown voltage with external flow speed. Paschen curves of the breakdown voltage V_c versus the product of pressure P_{flow} and emitter-collector distance d for plate discharges are given by

$$V_c = \frac{BP_{flow}d}{C + \ln(P_{flow}d)}, \quad (31)$$

with C a constant for what concerns this study. Trovato et al.'s measurement are within the range of 5-10 Torr.cm of the $P_{flow}d$ product, in air this corresponds to a nearly linear curve, albeit for a distinct configuration for which there are no known Paschen curves. Note that for such a small range, the product $\ln(P_{flow}d)$ can be approximated as a constant, so that the Paschen law above can be rewritten as $V_c \approx DP_{flow}d$, with $D = B/C + \ln(P_{flow}d)$ approximatively constant. For standard conditions corona discharges in air, breakdown voltage then becomes linear with external flow pressure. In the presence of an external flow, pressure will be modified so that breakdown voltage becomes: $V_c \approx Dd(P_{atm} + \Delta P) \approx V_c^0 + Dd\Delta P$, where $V_c^0 = DdP_{atm}$ is the ignition voltage without external flow speed, and ΔP is the pressure difference at a given point. Hence, as in [39], we hereby consider linear perturbation of the ignition voltage. For increasing Reynolds number (when $Re \gg 1$) the pressure becomes quadratic with flow speed u so that $V_c \approx V_c^0 - \frac{Dd}{2}\rho(\Delta u)^2$ with $(\Delta u)^2$ the relative quadratic flow speed at a given point, for positive pressure gradient this is negative and vice-versa. Evaluating pressures with and without external flow speed leads to $\Delta u^2 = (U_{in}^*)^2$, so that

$$V_c \approx Dd(P_{atm} - \frac{1}{2}\rho(U_{in}^*)^2) \approx V_c^0 - \frac{Dd}{2}\rho(U_{in}^*)^2 \quad (32)$$

Figure 13: Comparison of estimated breakdown voltage variation for different breakdown voltages with data from Trovato et al.

Thus breakdown voltage remains the same, though the effect of the external flow dims it, making breakdown voltage appear smaller, and not reach its actual value. The flow speed locally acts as a correction to the breakdown voltage without external flow speed. Trovato et al. measured the applied potential V_a at which breakdown occurred, which at the vicinity of the emitter according to our perturbative approach can be written as $V_a = V_a^0 + M_m V_a^1 = V_a^0 + M_m \beta V_a^{alt,1}$, where the second equation, explicitly shows the dependence with dimensionless inlet flow speed: $\beta = U_{in}^*/U_e^*$. For breakdown to occur, breakdown voltage has to be the same as the applied potential in the vicinity of the emitter: $V_c = V_a$ i.e. $V_c^0 - \frac{Dd}{2} \rho (U_{in}^*)^2 \approx V_a^0 + M_m \beta V_a^{alt,1}$. It is clear that $V_c^0 = V_a^0$, since when breakdown occurs in the absence of external flow speed the applied potential equals breakdown voltage, so that it comes to

$$V_a^{alt,1} \approx -\frac{Dd\rho}{2} \mu \frac{\varphi_a}{r_c^*} U_{in}^* \quad (33)$$

The external flow linearly decreases the applied potential around the discharge, leading to a likewise linear decrease of the applied potential at the emitter hence a linear increase of breakdown voltage as found in [20]. (33) is tested upon [20]'s measurements, for various likely applied potentials (since the zero velocity breakdown voltage is not provided in [20]) in figure 13 showing good agreement.

2.5. Velocity Conditions for Two-way Coupling : Practical application guidelines

Figure 14's top panel displays the current relative error $100(I - I_0)/I_0$ between the one-way approximation current I_0 and the observed one I , using data from Grosse et al. [19]. Errors greater than 20% are reached within about $0.04M_c^e$, which in practice corresponds to external flow speeds U_{in}^* between 5 to 10 m/s. A close look into Grosse et al.'s data is given in figure 14's center and bottom panels, highlighting where the two-way coupling becomes dominant compared to one-way, by computing the relative current intensity increase rate $(I - I_0)/I_0 U_{in}^*$. Center panel of figure 14 shows the

Figure 14: Top panel : Current relative increase with respect to no in-flow taken from the data of Grosse et al. [19]. Bottom panel : Current intensity increase rate versus external flow speed. Black lines represent iso-contours for various relative differences with the one-way approximation.

same error iso-contours as top panel for the relative current intensity increase rate. For external flow speeds larger than 5 m/s the one-way approximation error is larger than 10% and it levels-up to 20% when the flow speed reaches 8 m/s . Bottom panel shows that asymptotic behaviour of the current intensity increase rate with external flow speed (top panel) or M_c^e ranges (bottom panel) quickly emerges with the external flow speed. Hence, in regards to the electric response of corona discharge, the one-way approximation is valid up until less than $U_{in}^* < 5\text{ m/s}$ or $0.04\beta M_m$ i.e. $0.04M_c^e$ and two-way coupling effects becomes significant when $U_{in}^* > 10\text{ m/s}$ or $0.11M_c^e$.

Now inspecting the validity domain of the one-way approximation regarding the flow changes, figure 15 indicates that the one-way approximation remains valid for a much wider external flow velocity or M_c^e ranges. Figure15 left panels display

Figure 15: 9 Velocity field lines and velocity magnitude at the 0th order (left panel) and 1st order (right panel) at external flow speeds of 1 m/s (top panels) and 12 m/s (bottom panels) of the two collector NACA0012 configuration. The color map represent the velocity norm.

the one-way coupling velocity streamlines and magnitude for $U_{in}^* = 1m/s$ (top) and $U_{in}^* = 12m/s$ (bottom) whereas the right panels show their corresponding first order two-way coupling corrections which are two orders of magnitude smaller. When multiplied by M_m —from (23)— these corrections might even become four orders of magnitude smaller. This originates from the fact that the first order fluid correction is independent of the external flow speed, i.e β parameter, so that the external flow speed only acts on the zeroth order through its inlet boundary condition (9). It is worth mentioning that for $U_{in}^* = 1m/s$ (top left panel), the ionic wind is clearly visible in purple between the two NACA0012 collectors whereas when external flow increases (bottom left panel) the ionic wind is drawn by a larger external flow. Thus, when studying electric characteristics the two-way coupling should be used for

flows of more than a few meters per second or about $0.04M_c^e$, whereas when studying fluid characteristics the one-way approximation is valid at all external flow speed or M_c^e ranges. Note however, that these conclusions might only be valid up until more complex effects are considered such as, for example, compressible effects.

2.6. Unsteady and Compressible Effects

Whether high external flow velocity could rise unstable discharge regime is an interesting question which obviously encompass the scope of the present contribution. Even in the absence of external velocity the stability analysis of full corona discharge models is very scarce in the literature [27, 40] especially regarding complex electrode configurations having wide dimension ranges where, to our knowledge, none have been reported. However recent observations reported the opposite effect : high velocity fields alienates the breakdown threshold [20], with an apparent quadratic increase of the Paschen limit curve with the imposed external velocity. The deep physical reasons behind this observation are far from being understood and should deserve deeper investigations. On the other hand plasma-fluid couplings might not be the only responsible for possible instability to occur at high velocities. Inertia effects in the fluid are known to drive instabilities at high speed, even not completely quantitatively understood for NACA profiles at larger Reynolds number than those considered in our study. Regarding inertia effects in the vicinity of the emitter, the considered Reynolds number are ranging from 1 to 333, i.e. for $0.15 \text{ m/s} < U_{in}^* < 50 \text{ m/s}$ albeit already in the unsteady regime for higher speeds. Unsteady effects were dismissed in this study, since experimental measurements of electric characteristics followed linear trends. However they might be responsible for part of the current intensity predictions discrepancy at higher speed, in which case considering unsteady effects around the emitter might be relevant. Nonetheless, there are a couple of reasons supporting that unsteady effects do not impact charge generation around the emitter. Namely, charge generation due to external flow is mainly located at the emitter upstream (Cf. sec. 2.2), and this region is not greatly affected by unsteady effects. In addition, at emitter downstream where unsteady effects are most impactful, charges are mainly driven away by electro-drift so that the wake's advection only plays a secondary role. Concerning the validity of the incompressible approximation it follows from the standard Mach (M_c) number at atmospheric pressure, which remains small for all velocities considered in this paper. For instance, the macroscopic velocity of the ionic wind stays within the incompressible regime and is kept below few m/s. Neither does the maximal external flow speed which gives a fairly modest Mach number $M_c = 0.2$. At higher external flow speeds the incompressible approximation should be corrected following the standard Mach number at several levels, as density variations should need to be accounted for. Finally it is interesting to mention that the hereby provided steady-state approach should give an accurate description of the quasi-steady response to a low-frequency AC applied potential. This low frequency should nevertheless be smaller than the positive charges time-of-flight frequency within the system, i.e. smaller than $\mu_p E/d$ which can roughly be estimated as $2kHz$.

3. Conclusion

In this paper an asymptotically-based EAD analysis of a steady corona discharge blown by an external flow within a monolithic formulation has been presented.

This contribution relies on a previously developed two-domains approach for corona discharge modeling. The proposed formulation expands the previous one-way approximation using a new asymptotic expansion, allowing the derivation of two-way coupling between the fluid and CD to model EAD effects. This expansion is based upon small parameter M_m , being the ratio between macroscopic to microscopic ion velocities, recovering the (non-linear) one-way coupling approximation and providing the subsequent (linear) two-way coupling corrections to it. Numerical predictions have been compared with available experimental observations in two distinct experiments, showing a very satisfactory comparison (without any parameter adjustment). The agreement nevertheless degrades as the applied potential at the emitter increases, suggesting possible additional experimental effects such as back-discharge in some configurations. The numerical implementation has involved the numerical stabilization of the leading order Navier-Stokes weak formulation allowing to reach external speeds of up to 50m/s.

A closer look at the ion density distribution, shows that the external blow of the corona discharge increases both charge density and charge generation and also displaces the charge cloud downstream, closer to the collecting electrodes. The same goes for the electric potential. This is due to a non-local Poisson's electrostatic effect, that leads to an overall increase of the electric field in the ionization region by charge advection. Increasing the external flow field also deforms the electric field lines ever more, shrinking the collected charges region, and resulting in non-trivial electric-field stagnation points as well as downstream charge accumulations.

These results suggest many possible perspectives in order to analyse plasma/fluid interactions, in the presence of a strong external flow.

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Appendix A. Multi-scale two-domain modeling of the positive DC corona discharge

This appendix describes [21]'s approach to solve the leading order electrostatic problem using a multi-scale two-domain model of the DC corona discharge. In [21] the computational domain is split into two regions: an ionization region—inner domain Ω_1 —and a drift one—outer domain Ω_2 —. Since the electrons are localized within the ionization region of the plasma sheath, near the emitting electrode where the electric field is the highest thus enabling the Townsend cascade to arise. This region, being only a few times larger than the emitter diameter is very small compared to the outer one. Outside the sheath, unipolar charges are injected into the drift region, where they drift away producing ionic wind by colliding with neutral molecules. Since the physical mechanisms at play in these regions are very distinct from each other, they can be modeled separately and they communicate via matching conditions at both domains common frontier denoted Γ . [21] follow an expansion related to previously defined parameter ε .

Plasma-Fluid Coupling

31

Appendix A.1. Leading order problem

Neglecting $O(\delta_{\mu_e})$, $O(\frac{\exp(-1/\varepsilon)}{\varepsilon})$ as well as $O(\varepsilon^2)$ gives a leading order problem that reads for the inner domain Ω_1

$$\Delta\varphi_{\Omega_1}^0 = 0 \quad (\text{A.1})$$

$$\nabla \cdot [-n_{p\Omega_1}^0 \nabla\varphi_{\Omega_1}^0 - \frac{1}{P_e} \nabla n_{p\Omega_1}^0] = \alpha^0 n_{e\Omega_1}^0 E_{\Omega_1}^0 \quad (\text{A.2})$$

$$\nabla \cdot [n_{e\Omega_1}^0 \nabla\varphi_{\Omega_1}^0 - \frac{\delta_{\mu_e}}{P_e} \nabla n_{e\Omega_1}^0] = (\alpha^0 - \eta^0) n_{e\Omega_1}^0 E_{\Omega_1}^0 \quad (\text{A.3})$$

$$\nabla \cdot [n_{n\Omega_1}^0 \nabla\varphi_{\Omega_1}^0 - \frac{1}{P_e} \nabla n_{n\Omega_1}^0] = \eta^0 n_{e\Omega_1}^0 E_{\Omega_1}^0 \quad (\text{A.4})$$

where α^0 and η^0 are provided in [21]. In the outer domain Ω_2 the leading order reads

$$\Delta\varphi_{\Omega_2}^0 = -n_{p\Omega_2}^0 + n_{p\Omega_2}^0 \quad (\text{A.5})$$

$$\nabla \cdot [-n_{p\Omega_2}^0 \nabla\varphi_{\Omega_2}^0 - \frac{1}{P_e} \nabla n_{p\Omega_2}^0] = \gamma S^0 \quad (\text{A.6})$$

$$\nabla \cdot [n_{n\Omega_2}^0 \nabla\varphi_{\Omega_2}^0 - \frac{1}{P_e} \nabla n_{n\Omega_2}^0] = 0 \quad (\text{A.7})$$

Where γ , S^0 are the same as in [21]. Yet again, this is the same electrostatic problem as in [21], with the addition of diffusion fluxes. The fluid problem can be solved in both domains simultaneously as $O(\delta_{\mu_e})$ are neglected leading to

$$\mathbf{u}_{\Omega}^0 \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u}_{\Omega}^0 = -\nabla p_{\Omega}^0 + \frac{1}{R_e} \Delta \mathbf{u}_{\Omega}^0 - (n_{p\Omega}^0 - n_{n\Omega}^0) \nabla \varphi_{\Omega}^0 \quad (\text{A.8})$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}_{\Omega}^0 = 0 \quad (\text{A.9})$$

This is the same fluid problem as in [25]. Note that the electron densities are neglected in the Coulomb forcing.

Appendix A.2. First order problem

Tackling the first order then becomes a very similar task as the asymptotic expansion of the leading order. In fact it is very close to the linearized form of the leading order

system, with a source term from the leading order charge advection. It reads in Ω_1

$$\Delta\varphi_{\Omega_1}^1 = 0 \quad (\text{A.10})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla \cdot [-n_{p\Omega_1}^1 \nabla\varphi_{\Omega_1}^0 - n_{p\Omega_1}^0 \nabla\varphi_{\Omega_1}^1 - \frac{1}{P_e} \nabla n_{p\Omega_1}^1] = \\ \alpha^1 n_{e\Omega_1}^0 E_{\Omega_1}^0 + \alpha^0 n_{e\Omega_1}^1 E_{\Omega_1}^0 + \alpha^0 n_{e\Omega_1}^0 E_{\Omega_1}^1 - \nabla \cdot (n_{p\Omega_1}^0 \mathbf{u}_{\Omega_1}^0) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.11})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla \cdot [-n_{e\Omega_1}^0 \nabla\varphi_{\Omega_1}^1 - n_{e\Omega_1}^1 \nabla\varphi_{\Omega_1}^0 - \frac{\delta\mu_e}{P_e} \nabla n_{e\Omega_1}^1] = \\ (\alpha^1 - \eta^1) n_{e\Omega_1}^0 E_{\Omega_1}^0 + (\alpha^0 - \eta^0) n_{e\Omega_1}^1 E_{\Omega_1}^0 + (\alpha^0 - \eta^0) n_{e\Omega_1}^0 E_{\Omega_1}^1 - \nabla \cdot (n_{e\Omega_1}^0 \mathbf{u}_{\Omega_1}^0) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.12})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla \cdot [-n_{n\Omega_1}^0 \nabla\varphi_{\Omega_1}^1 - n_{n\Omega_1}^1 \nabla\varphi_{\Omega_1}^0 - \frac{1}{P_e} \nabla n_{n\Omega_1}^1] = \\ \eta^1 n_{e\Omega_1}^0 E_{\Omega_1}^0 + \eta^0 n_{e\Omega_1}^1 E_{\Omega_1}^0 + \eta^0 n_{e\Omega_1}^0 E_{\Omega_1}^1 - \nabla \cdot (n_{n\Omega_1}^0 \mathbf{u}_{\Omega_1}^0) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.13})$$

where α^1 and η^1 are as in [21]. In Ω_2 the leading order reads

$$\Delta\varphi_{\Omega_2}^1 = -n_{p\Omega_2}^1 \quad (\text{A.14})$$

$$\nabla \cdot [-n_{p\Omega_2}^1 \nabla\varphi_{\Omega_2}^0 - n_{p\Omega_2}^0 \nabla\varphi_{\Omega_2}^1 - \frac{1}{P_e} \nabla n_{p\Omega_2}^1] = \gamma S^1 - \nabla \cdot (n_{p\Omega_2}^0 \mathbf{u}_{\Omega_2}^0) \quad (\text{A.15})$$

$$\nabla \cdot [n_{n\Omega_2}^1 \nabla\varphi_{\Omega_2}^0 - n_{n\Omega_2}^0 \nabla\varphi_{\Omega_2}^1 - \frac{1}{P_e} \nabla n_{n\Omega_2}^1] = -\nabla \cdot (n_{n\Omega_2}^0 \mathbf{u}_{\Omega_2}^0) \quad (\text{A.16})$$

Once again, this is the same electrostatic problem as in [21], with the addition of diffusive effects. The fluid problem can be solved in both domains simultaneously as $O(\delta\mu_e)$ effects are neglected this will be further justified later on, thus leading to

$$\mathbf{u}_{\Omega}^0 \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u}_{\Omega}^1 + \mathbf{u}_{\Omega}^1 \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u}_{\Omega}^0 = -\nabla p_{\Omega}^1 + \frac{1}{Re} \Delta \mathbf{u}_{\Omega}^1 - (n_{p\Omega}^1 - n_{n\Omega}^1) \nabla \varphi_{\Omega}^0 - (n_{p\Omega}^0 - n_{n\Omega}^0) \nabla \varphi_{\Omega}^1 \quad (\text{A.17})$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}_{\Omega}^1 = 0. \quad (\text{A.18})$$

In addition to the previous references, [25] provides additional information about the derivation of the dimensionless multi-scale asymptotic formulation.

Appendix A.2.1. Matching and boundary conditions Boundary conditions can easily be expressed as they are either all homogeneous or constant Dirichlet conditions which only act at the leading order and become homogeneous Dirichlet conditions at first order.

- The electric potential with Dirichlet boundary conditions become

$$\varphi_{|\partial\Omega_e}^0 = 1 \quad \& \quad \varphi_{|\partial\Omega_c}^0 = 0 \quad (\text{A.19})$$

$$\varphi_{|\partial\Omega_e}^1 = 0 \quad \& \quad \varphi_{|\partial\Omega_c}^1 = 0. \quad (\text{A.20})$$

At the interface $\Gamma = \Omega_1 \cap \Omega_2$, the potential has to verify a "two-way" constraint as described by Magoulès et al. in [37], meaning that both φ_{Ω_1} and φ_{Ω_2} are required to verify

$$\varphi_{\Omega_1|\Gamma} = \varphi_{\Omega_2|\Gamma} \quad (\text{A.21})$$

$$\nabla\varphi_{\Omega_1} \cdot \mathbf{n}_{1|\Gamma} = -\varphi_{\Omega_2} \cdot \mathbf{n}_{2|\Gamma}, \quad (\text{A.22})$$

where the minus sign comes from the outward sign of the outward normal.

- The charge densities follow hyperbolic equations at the electrodes, as the Peclet number is of the order of 10^4 , so that the border conditions become

$$\mathbf{j}_p \cdot \mathbf{n}_{1|\partial\Omega_e} := n_p \partial_n \varphi|_{\partial\Omega_e} = 0 \quad \& \quad \mathbf{j}_e \cdot \mathbf{n}_{2|\partial\Omega_c} := n_e \partial_n \varphi|_{\partial\Omega_c} = 0 \quad (\text{A.23})$$

$$\& \quad \mathbf{j}_n \cdot \mathbf{n}_{2|\partial\Omega_c} := n_n \partial_n \varphi|_{\partial\Omega_c} = 0 \quad (\text{A.24})$$

which become respectively at the leading order :

$$n_p^0 \partial_n \varphi|_{\partial\Omega_e}^0 = 0 \quad \& \quad n_e^0 \partial_n \varphi|_{\partial\Omega_c}^0 = 0 \quad (\text{A.25})$$

$$\& \quad n_n^0 \partial_n \varphi|_{\partial\Omega_c}^0 = 0 \quad (\text{A.26})$$

$$(\text{A.27})$$

And at the first order :

$$n_p^0 \partial_n \varphi|_{\partial\Omega_e}^1 + n_p^1 \partial_n \varphi|_{\partial\Omega_e}^0 = 0 \quad \& \quad n_e^0 \partial_n \varphi|_{\partial\Omega_c}^1 + n_e^1 \partial_n \varphi|_{\partial\Omega_c}^0 = 0. \quad (\text{A.28})$$

$$\& \quad n_n^0 \partial_n \varphi|_{\partial\Omega_c}^1 + n_n^1 \partial_n \varphi|_{\partial\Omega_c}^0 = 0. \quad (\text{A.29})$$

$$(\text{A.30})$$

As for the matching conditions for the ion flux, given that positive charges travel from the emitter to the collector, i.e. from Ω_1 to Ω_2 , the ion flux in Ω_2 must be injected with the ion flux coming from Ω_1 and vice-versa, and just as well to negative ions. So that

$$\mathbf{j}_{p\Omega_2} \cdot \mathbf{n}_{2|\Gamma} = -\mathbf{j}_{p\Omega_1} \cdot \mathbf{n}_{1|\Gamma} \quad (\text{A.31})$$

$$\mathbf{j}_{n\Omega_2} \cdot \mathbf{n}_{2|\Gamma} = -\mathbf{j}_{n\Omega_1} \cdot \mathbf{n}_{1|\Gamma} \quad (\text{A.32})$$

As few secondary electrons are created in the drift region Ω_2 by photo-ionization, it feeds the ionization region Ω_1 through the interface Γ leading to the electron flux

$$\mathbf{j}_{e\Omega_2} \cdot \mathbf{n}_{1|\Gamma} = -\mathbf{j}_{e\Omega_2} \cdot \mathbf{n}_{2|\Gamma} \quad (\text{A.33})$$

The photo-ionization in the drift domain depends on the ionization rate in Ω_1 in a complex way. A detailed derivation is performed in [21] leading to

$$\mathbf{j}_e \cdot \mathbf{n}_{\Omega_2|\Gamma} = j_{e|\Gamma}^0 + \varepsilon j_{e|\Gamma}^1(\theta) + O(\varepsilon^2), \quad (\text{A.34})$$

with $j_{e|\Gamma}^0$ and $\varepsilon j_{e|\Gamma}^1(\theta)$ given in [21].

- Both the normal electric field and the ion charge flux are imposed null at the outer boundaries of the domain

$$\mathbf{E}^0 \cdot \mathbf{n}_{|\partial\Omega_{in} \cup \partial\Omega_{out} \cup \partial\Omega_{top} \cup \partial\Omega_{bot}} = 0 \quad \& \quad \mathbf{j}_p^0 \cdot \mathbf{n}_{|\partial\Omega_{in} \cup \partial\Omega_{out} \cup \partial\Omega_{top} \cup \partial\Omega_{bot}} = 0 \quad (\text{A.35})$$

$$\& \quad \mathbf{j}_n^0 \cdot \mathbf{n}_{|\partial\Omega_{in} \cup \partial\Omega_{out} \cup \partial\Omega_{top} \cup \partial\Omega_{bot}} = 0 \quad (\text{A.36})$$

$$\mathbf{E}^1 \cdot \mathbf{n}_{|\partial\Omega_{in} \cup \partial\Omega_{out} \cup \partial\Omega_{top} \cup \partial\Omega_{bot}} = 0 \quad \& \quad \mathbf{j}_p^1 \cdot \mathbf{n}_{|\partial\Omega_{in} \cup \partial\Omega_{out} \cup \partial\Omega_{top} \cup \partial\Omega_{bot}} = 0 \quad (\text{A.37})$$

$$\& \quad \mathbf{j}_n^1 \cdot \mathbf{n}_{|\partial\Omega_{in} \cup \partial\Omega_{out} \cup \partial\Omega_{top} \cup \partial\Omega_{bot}} = 0 \quad (\text{A.38})$$

- As for the fluid boundary conditions, we apply a no-slip velocity at the emitter and collector surfaces, and a stress-free velocity condition over the downstream and lateral boundaries. As these are linear equations, they will be applied identically at the leading and first order, as will the tangential stress-free condition on the inlet boundary. Finally, for the inlet boundary, we impose a constant velocity $U_{in}^*/U_e^* \equiv \beta$ will lead to :

$$\mathbf{u}^0 \cdot \mathbf{n}|_{\partial\Omega_{in}} = \beta \quad \& \quad \mathbf{u}^1 \cdot \mathbf{n}|_{\partial\Omega_{in}} = 0 \quad (\text{A.39})$$

Appendix A.3. Two-domain variational formulation of the first order problem

We will now give the variational formulation associated with the first order electrical problem. As explained earlier, we are basing ourselves on Monrolin et al.'s approach [21] that consisted on modeling the physics on the ionization region and on the drift region separately and imposing continuity between electric potential and field as well as ion and electron fluxes on the border between the two domains. So each domain has its own specific variational formulation and communication between domains is achieved via the use of Lagrangian multipliers.

In Monrolin et al.'s work, modeling is achieved via an asymptotic expansion with the parameter ε , so that they have a leading order and first order electric problem on each domain communicating with Lagrangian multipliers. Our approach is analogous, however our expansion is not along the parameter ε but along the parameter M_m , but this does not seem to have an impact on the respective leading order and first order formulations aside from the source term of (A.10)-(A.14). So the bi-linear form of our first order electric problem (A.10)-(A.14) will be the same as Monrolin et al.'s., and it will suffice to change the linear form associated with it to take into account our source term, which were the last terms of the three last equations of (27).

We will set the following spaces as $\mathcal{U}_1, \mathcal{V}_1, \mathcal{W}_1, \mathcal{Z}_1 \subset H^1(\Omega_1)$ and $\mathcal{U}_2, \mathcal{V}_2, \mathcal{W}_2 \subset H^1(\Omega_2)$. So noting the bilinear functions $\mathcal{F}_{\Omega_1}^1$ and $\mathcal{F}_{\Omega_2}^1$ the variational formulation of the strong equations, similar to Monrolin et al.'s and defining as they did Lagrange multipliers associated with potential λ_φ , positive and negative charge flux continuity λ_p and λ_n , and imposed electron flux λ_e at Γ , with test functions respectively $\mu_\varphi, \mu_p, \mu_n$ and μ_e , and the functional space associated with Lagrange multiplier adjoin test-functions on Γ is $\mathcal{R} \subset H^{-1/2}(\Gamma)$ [37]. So that the weak formulation associated with the first order electric problem reads: Find $(\varphi_{\Omega_1}^1, n_{p,\Omega_1}^1, n_{n,\Omega_1}^1, n_{e,\Omega_1}^1, \varphi_{\Omega_2}^1, n_{p,\Omega_2}^1, n_{n,\Omega_2}^1, \lambda_\varphi, \lambda_p, \lambda_e) \in \mathcal{U}_1 \times \mathcal{V}_1 \times \mathcal{W}_1 \times \mathcal{Z}_1 \times \mathcal{U}_2 \times \mathcal{V}_2 \times \mathcal{W}_2 \times \mathcal{R} \times \mathcal{R} \times \mathcal{R}$ such that

$$\mathcal{F}_{\Omega_1}^1 \left[\begin{pmatrix} \varphi_{\Omega_1}^1 \\ n_{p,\Omega_1}^1 \\ n_{n,\Omega_1}^1 \\ n_{e,\Omega_1}^1 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} \varphi_{\Omega_1}^{1,\dagger} \\ n_{p,\Omega_1}^{1,\dagger} \\ n_{n,\Omega_1}^{1,\dagger} \\ n_{e,\Omega_1}^{1,\dagger} \end{pmatrix} \right] + \begin{pmatrix} -\int_{\Gamma} \lambda_{\varphi} \varphi_{\Omega_1}^{1,\dagger} \\ -\int_{\Gamma} \lambda_p n_{p,\Omega_1}^{1,\dagger} \\ -\int_{\Gamma} \lambda_n n_{n,\Omega_1}^{1,\dagger} \\ -\int_{\Gamma} \lambda_e n_{e,\Omega_1}^{1,\dagger} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ -\int_{\Omega_1} \nabla \cdot (n_{p,\Omega_1}^0 \mathbf{u}_{\Omega_1}^0) n_{p,\Omega_1}^{1,\dagger} \\ -\int_{\Omega_1} \nabla \cdot (n_{n,\Omega_1}^0 \mathbf{u}_{\Omega_1}^0) n_{n,\Omega_1}^{1,\dagger} \\ -\int_{\Omega_1} \nabla \cdot (n_{e,\Omega_1}^0 \mathbf{u}_{\Omega_1}^0) n_{e,\Omega_1}^{1,\dagger} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\forall (\varphi_{\Omega_1}^{1,\dagger}, n_{p,\Omega_1}^{1,\dagger}, n_{n,\Omega_1}^{1,\dagger}, n_{e,\Omega_1}^{1,\dagger}) \in \mathcal{U}_1 \times \mathcal{V}_1 \times \mathcal{W}_1 \times \mathcal{Z}_1$$
(A.40)

$$\mathcal{F}_{\Omega_2}^1 \left[\begin{pmatrix} \varphi_{\Omega_2}^1 \\ n_{p,\Omega_2}^1 \\ n_{n,\Omega_2}^1 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} \varphi_{\Omega_2}^{1,\dagger} \\ n_{p,\Omega_2}^{1,\dagger} \\ n_{n,\Omega_2}^{1,\dagger} \end{pmatrix} \right] + \begin{pmatrix} \int_{\Gamma} \lambda_{\varphi} \varphi_{\Omega_2}^{1,\dagger} \\ \int_{\Gamma} \lambda_p \lambda_{p,\Omega_2}^{1,\dagger} \\ \int_{\Gamma} \lambda_n \lambda_{n,\Omega_2}^{1,\dagger} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ -\int_{\Omega_2} \nabla \cdot (n_{p,\Omega_2}^0 \mathbf{u}_{\Omega_2}^0) n_{p,\Omega_2}^{1,\dagger} \\ -\int_{\Omega_2} \nabla \cdot (n_{n,\Omega_2}^0 \mathbf{u}_{\Omega_2}^0) n_{n,\Omega_2}^{1,\dagger} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\forall (\varphi_{\Omega_2}^{1,\dagger}, n_{p,\Omega_2}^{1,\dagger}, n_{n,\Omega_2}^{1,\dagger}) \in \mathcal{U}_2 \times \mathcal{V}_2 \times \mathcal{W}_2$$
(A.41)

$$\int_{\Gamma} \mu_{\varphi} (\varphi_{\Omega_2}^1 - \varphi_{\Omega_1}^1) = 0 \quad \forall \mu_{\varphi} \in \mathcal{R}$$
(A.42)

$$\int_{\Gamma} \mu_p (n_{p,\Omega_2}^1 \partial_n \varphi_{\Omega_2}^0 + n_{p,\Omega_2}^0 \partial_n \varphi_{\Omega_2}^1 - n_{p,\Omega_1}^1 \partial_n \varphi_{\Omega_1}^0 - n_{p,\Omega_1}^0 \partial_n \varphi_{\Omega_1}^1) = 0 \quad \forall \mu_p \in \mathcal{R}$$
(A.43)

$$\int_{\Gamma} \mu_n (n_{n,\Omega_2}^1 \partial_n \varphi_{\Omega_2}^0 + n_{n,\Omega_2}^0 \partial_n \varphi_{\Omega_2}^1 - n_{n,\Omega_1}^1 \partial_n \varphi_{\Omega_1}^0 - n_{n,\Omega_1}^0 \partial_n \varphi_{\Omega_1}^1) = 0 \quad \forall \mu_n \in \mathcal{R}$$
(A.44)

$$\int_{\Gamma} \mu_e (\lambda_e - j_{e|\Gamma}^1) = 0 \quad \forall \mu_e \in \mathcal{R}$$
(A.45)

Lastly, the first order fluid problem can be simply implemented as it is a linear problem, we will not detail its weak formulation and implementation, as it can be seen as a sole iteration of the previously detailed leading order problem (C.13) with a second member corresponding to the last term of (A.17).

Appendix B. Two-way coupling with Kaptzov approximation

The so-called Kaptzov hypothesis, is the assumption the electric field at the emitting electrode E_a is constant, E_a is the Peek electric field. This assumption is often used to simplify corona modeling and seems to yield accurate results within a good range of configurations [32]. Furthermore, this assumption has been theoretically justified in the case of an axis-symmetric configuration by Monrolin et al. [28]. One can find more detail about this approximation in appendix A. from [21].

The use of the Kaptzov approximation allows for simplified numerical simulations, as it shrinks down the ionization region into a boundary with an associated boundary layer condition. For an applied potential φ_a^* , meaning a respective electric field E_a , the charge density injected at the discharge frontier is adjusted so that the surface electric field reached the desired value. It is indeed a fully coupled approach, solved via Newton-Raphson steps.

Two-way coupling of this drift region model with an external flow with the means of

our linear expansion following the parameter M_m can so far only be achieved via the use of a tuning parameter a , as we don't know the effect of the external flow on the electric field E_a . This tuning parameter would be user defined by fitting it with the data.

The Kaptzov assumption would then be limited, as it could never make trustworthy *a priori* predictions of current intensity with external flow-speed. In fact, the tuning parameter is configuration dependent, and any change in the geometry or applied potential would change it. There is no way to know the correct value of the tuning parameter a without a set of experimental data of the studied configuration.

Nevertheless, this model is still of interest as it allows us to see more clearly into the corona discharge two-domain model as well as shows its effectiveness.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \Delta\varphi = -(n_p - n_n - \delta_{\mu_e} n_e) \\ \nabla \cdot [n_p(-\nabla\varphi + M_m \mathbf{u}) - \frac{1}{P_e} \nabla n_p] = 0 \\ \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla p - \frac{1}{R_e} \Delta \mathbf{u} = -n_p \nabla \varphi \\ \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0 \end{array} \right. \quad (\text{B.1})$$

$$\varphi|_{\Gamma} = 1 \quad \varphi|_{\partial\Omega_c} = 0 \quad (\text{B.2})$$

$$n_p^{\mathbf{E}} \cdot \mathbf{n}|_{\Gamma} = \lambda_{\varphi} \quad \partial_n \varphi|_{\Gamma} = E_a \quad (\text{B.3})$$

$$\mathbf{u}|_{\Gamma} = \mathbf{0} \quad \mathbf{u}|_{\partial\Omega_c} = \mathbf{0} \quad (\text{B.4})$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{n}|_{\partial\Omega_{top} \cup \partial\Omega_{bot} \cup \partial\Omega_{out}} = 0 \quad \mathbf{t} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{n}|_{\partial\Omega_{in}} = 0 \quad (\text{B.5})$$

$$\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n}|_{\partial\Omega_{in}} = \beta \quad (\text{B.6})$$

We can then apply our linear expansion, and get a leading order and as first order problem. Note that the expansion applied to the electric field in Γ is $\partial_n \varphi|_{\Gamma} = E_a(1 + aM_m + O(M_m^2))$. The leading order problem is thus the one-way problem described in Picella et al.'s [25] and the first order problem is :

$$\Delta\varphi_{\Omega_2}^1 = -n_{p\Omega_2}^1 \quad (\text{B.7})$$

$$\nabla \cdot [-n_{p\Omega_2}^1 \nabla \varphi_{\Omega_2}^0 - n_{p\Omega_2}^0 \nabla \varphi_{\Omega_2}^1 - \frac{1}{P_e} \nabla n_{p\Omega_2}^1] = 0 \quad (\text{B.8})$$

$$\mathbf{u}_{\Omega}^0 \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u}_{\Omega}^1 + \mathbf{u}_{\Omega}^1 \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u}_{\Omega}^0 = -\nabla p^1 + \frac{1}{R_e} \Delta \mathbf{u}_{\Omega}^1 - n_{p\Omega}^1 \nabla \varphi_{\Omega}^0 - n_{p\Omega}^0 \nabla \varphi_{\Omega}^1 \quad (\text{B.9})$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}_{\Omega}^1 = 0 \quad (\text{B.10})$$

With boundary conditions

$$\varphi|_{\Gamma} = 0 \quad \varphi|_{\partial\Omega_c} = 0 \quad (\text{B.11})$$

$$(n_p^1 \mathbf{E}^0 + n_p^0 \mathbf{E}^1) \cdot \mathbf{n}|_{\Gamma} = \lambda_{\varphi} \quad \partial_n \varphi|_{\Gamma} = aE_a \quad (\text{B.12})$$

$$\mathbf{u}|_{\Gamma} = \mathbf{0} \quad \mathbf{u}|_{\partial\Omega_c} = \mathbf{0} \quad (\text{B.13})$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}^1 \cdot \mathbf{n}|_{\partial\Omega_{top} \cup \partial\Omega_{bot} \cup \partial\Omega_{out}} = 0 \quad \mathbf{t} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}^1 \cdot \mathbf{n}|_{\partial\Omega_{in}} = 0 \quad (\text{B.14})$$

$$\mathbf{u}^1 \cdot \mathbf{n}|_{\partial\Omega_{in}} = 0 \quad (\text{B.15})$$

Appendix C. Stabilized variational formulation of the Navier-Stokes problem

The steady Navier-Stokes equations in (A.8) being non-linear is solved with a Newton method following [25]. To reach external speeds, as high as 50 m/s, usual Navier-Stokes Newton iterations doesn't always converge. Therefore stabilized form of Navier-Stokes equations are used following [41] for the Oseen equations (C.1). This approach is common when solving the Navier-Stokes equations by applying a fixed point or Newton-type iteration, as the linearized Navier-Stokes reads as Oseen one

$$\begin{cases} L_{Os}(\mathbf{b}, [\mathbf{u}, p]) = -\nu \Delta \mathbf{u} + (\mathbf{b} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{u} + \nabla p = f & \text{in } \Omega \\ \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0 & \text{in } \Omega \end{cases} \quad (\text{C.1})$$

with f the Coulomb forcing. The mesh is built so as to create an admissible triangulation, as well as verifying the other properties required from functional spaces for velocity and pressure : $\mathbf{W}_h^{2,2} := \mathbf{V}_h^2 \times \mathbf{Q}_h^2$, with $\mathbf{V}_h^2 := H_0^1(\Omega) \cap X_h^2(\Omega)$, $\mathbf{Q}_h^2 := L_0^2(\Omega) \cap X_h^2(\Omega)$, with $H_0^1(\Omega)$, $L_0^2(\Omega)$ and $X_h^2(\Omega)$ defined in [41]. This permits to use the stabilization schemes developed in [41].

Setting the functional scalar products as $(u, v) := \int_{\Omega} uv \, d\Omega$ for scalar functions, $(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}) := \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{v} \, d\Omega$ for vector functions and $(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}) := \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{u} : \mathbf{v} \, d\Omega$ for tensors fields. The weak formulation of the steady Navier-Stokes equations, is set by finding $(\mathbf{u}^0, p^0) \in \mathbf{W}_h^{2,2}$ such that

$$\mathcal{NS}(\mathbf{u}^0, [\mathbf{u}^0, p^0], (\mathbf{v}, q)) = \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{v}, q) \quad (\text{C.2})$$

Where

$$\mathcal{NS}(\mathbf{u}^0, [\mathbf{u}^0, p^0], (\mathbf{v}, q)) = \frac{1}{Re} (\nabla \mathbf{u}^0, \nabla \mathbf{v}) + ((\mathbf{u}^0 \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{u}^0, \mathbf{v}) + b(\mathbf{v}, p^0) - b(\mathbf{u}^0, q) \quad (\text{C.3})$$

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{v}, q) = (-n_p^0 \nabla \varphi^0, \mathbf{v}) \quad (\text{C.4})$$

$$b(\mathbf{v}, p) = -(p^0, \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}). \quad (\text{C.5})$$

To solve this equation a Newton linearization is used, so that the incremental solutions given by solving linearized weak formulation of the steady Navier-Stokes equations is defined as finding $[\delta \mathbf{u}^0, \delta p^0] \in \mathbf{W}_h^{2,2}$ such that

$$\delta \mathcal{NS}(\mathbf{u}^0, [\delta \mathbf{u}^0, \delta p^0], (\mathbf{v}, q)) = \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{u}^0, [\mathbf{u}^0, p^0], (\mathbf{v}, q)) \quad (\text{C.6})$$

with $\delta \mathcal{NS}$ and \mathcal{F} operators defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \delta \mathcal{NS}(\mathbf{u}^0, [\delta \mathbf{u}^0, \delta p^0], (\mathbf{v}, q)) &:= \frac{1}{Re} (\nabla \delta \mathbf{u}^0, \nabla \mathbf{v}) + ((\delta \mathbf{u}^0 \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{u}^0, \mathbf{v}) + \\ &((\mathbf{u}^0 \cdot \nabla) \delta \mathbf{u}^0, \mathbf{v}) + b(\mathbf{v}, \delta p^0) - b(\delta \mathbf{u}^0, q) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.7})$$

$$\mathcal{F}(\mathbf{u}^0, [\mathbf{u}^0, p^0], (\mathbf{v}, q)) := -\mathcal{NS}(\mathbf{u}^0, [\mathbf{u}^0, p^0], (\mathbf{v}, q)) + \mathcal{L}((\mathbf{v}, q)), \quad (\text{C.8})$$

$$(\text{C.9})$$

where \mathcal{F} is the Newton's residue. As previously mentioned, the Newton iteration doesn't always converge, possibly because continuous solution display significant structures not sufficiently captured by the FE mesh, e.g sharp boundary layers [42]. Furthermore capturing the sharpness is restricted by the chosen finite element

spaces. The mesh resolution being usually coarser than the layer width, for numerical solution with sharp layers, strong residual in the layer regions will likely be large. Hence residual and pressure-based stabilizations are introduced, respectively helping regulate problems arising with numerical viscosity (SUPG/PSPG) and with the mass conservation (Grad-div). Defining

$$L_{\delta NS}(\mathbf{u}, [\delta \mathbf{u}, \delta p]) := -\frac{1}{Re} \Delta \delta \mathbf{u} + (\delta \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{u} + (\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) \delta \mathbf{u} + \nabla \delta p \quad (\text{C.10})$$

$$L_{NS}(\mathbf{u}, [\mathbf{u}, p]) := -\frac{1}{Re} \Delta \mathbf{u} + (\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{u} + \nabla p - n_p \nabla \varphi, \quad (\text{C.11})$$

Defined this way $L_{\delta NS}$ takes the form of an Oseen operator as in (C.1) where $\mathbf{b} = \mathbf{u}$. The SUPG/PSPG/Grad-div stabilized weak formulation for linearized Navier-Stokes is defined for a given triangulation \mathcal{T}_h of Ω , as finding $(\delta \mathbf{u}^0, \delta p^0) \in W_h^{2,2}$ such that

$$\delta \mathcal{N} \mathcal{S}_{spg}(\mathbf{u}^0, [\delta \mathbf{u}^0, \delta p^0], (\mathbf{v}, q)) = \mathcal{F}_{spg}(\mathbf{u}^0, [\mathbf{u}^0, p^0], (\mathbf{v}, q)), \quad (\text{C.12})$$

where,

$$\delta \mathcal{N} \mathcal{S}_{spg}(\mathbf{u}^0, [\delta \mathbf{u}^0, \delta p^0]) := \delta \mathcal{N} \mathcal{S}(\mathbf{u}^0, [\delta \mathbf{u}^0, \delta p^0]) + \underbrace{\sum_{T \in \mathcal{T}_h} \gamma_T (\nabla \cdot \delta \mathbf{u}^0, \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v})}_{\text{grad-div stabilization}} \quad (\text{C.13})$$

$$+ \underbrace{\sum_{T \in \mathcal{T}_h} \tau_T (L_{\delta NS}(\mathbf{u}^0; \delta \mathbf{u}^0, p^0), (\mathbf{u}^0 \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v} + \nabla q)_T}_{\text{SUPG/PSPG stabilization}} \quad (\text{C.14})$$

$$\mathcal{F}_{spg}((\mathbf{v}, q)) = \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{u}^0, [\mathbf{u}^0, p^0], (\mathbf{v}, q)) + \quad (\text{C.15})$$

$$\underbrace{\sum_{T \in \mathcal{T}_h} \tau_T (L_{NS}(\mathbf{u}^0, [\mathbf{u}^0, p^0]), (\mathbf{u}^0 \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v} + \nabla q)_T}_{\text{SUPG/PSPG stabilization}} \quad (\text{C.16})$$

Where γ_T is the user's defined parameter associated with the grad-div stabilization and is $\sim O(1)$, τ_T is the SUPG/PSPG stabilization parameter chosen as

$$\tau_T = \tau \left(\frac{r^4}{Re h_T^2} + \frac{r \|\mathbf{u}\|_{L^\infty(T)}}{h_T} \right) \quad (\text{C.17})$$

where r is the polynomial degree of the approximation, h_T the mesh size, and τ is user defined. The choice of stabilization parameter has been studied in various papers [43, 42, 44, 45]. Here, a second order polynomial is chosen for both velocity and pressure. As for the choice of parameters $\gamma = 1$ and $\tau = 10^{-4}$ have allowed convergence up to external velocity 50 m/s in the case of a wire-to-cylinder configuration, with a 3 cm radius cylinder.

Appendix D. On the choice of user-defined stabilization parameters τ and γ

In this section we will give some detail on how we have selected the stabilization parameters. Heuristics for calculating the user defined stabilization parameters for

Figure D1: Scatter plots of the critical external flow speed as a function of the choice of the user defined parameters τ and γ . The critical external flow speed is the speed at which we last managed to converge in the Navier-Stokes simulations.

the SUPG/PSPG stabilization τ and for the grad-div stabilization γ . Heuristics for the choice of the parameters δ can be found in [44] and [46], and more details on the γ parameters can be found in [46].

In figure D1, we present the scatter plots of the critical external flow speed as a function of the choice of the user defined parameters τ and γ . The critical external flow speed is the speed at which we last managed to converge in the Navier-Stokes simulations, briefly justifying the reason behind our parameter choice for τ and γ .

The choice of these parameters was done with a trial and error procedure, where we tried to increase inlet flow speed for a given parameter choice, which would imply that our simulation would need to converge. So that for a each parameter we would reach critical external flow speed velocities, after which our Navier-Stokes simulations would no longer be able to converge. We must notice though that this procedure is configuration dependent, as well as mesh dependent. This last point is relevant, as we adapt our mesh with the increase of the external flow speed. Once we found a parameter that seemed to work better than the other, we used it to adapt our continuations so as to increase the inlet flow speed.

Following this method, we tested parameters for the *grad - div* stabilization ranging from 1 to 10, and found $\gamma = 1$ to work the best, as shown in figure D1. As for the SUPG/PSPG-stabilization parameter we tested several values and found that values around 0.01 seem to ensure convergence for higher speeds, as shown in figure D1.

Appendix E. Insight on the meshes and automatic meshing

In this section, some insight on the meshes used for computations is given. Figure E1 shows the typical mesh used in the case of the two NACA0012 collectors for the 0th (A.1) (A.5) and 1st (A.10), (A.14) order electric problem computations. It contains 55398 points and forms a number of 110426 triangles. A zoom around the emitter is made to showcase the mesh refinement around the emitter. The emitter is discretised with fifty points, and an exponential refinement towards the emitter is made in a radius of four times that of the emitter so as to account for the steep gradients of the boundary layer of ion and electron densities. This refinement is handmade rather than automatic.

Figure E1: Mesh used in the case of the two NACA0012 collectors for the 0th (A.1) (A.5) and 1st (A.10), (A.14) order electric problem computations it contains 55398 points and forms a number of 110426 triangles, with a close up of the refinement around the emitter.

Figure E2 shows the typical mesh used in the case of the two NACA0012 collectors for the fluid (A.8) problem computations. It contains 54252 points and forms a number of 106970 triangles. A zoom around one of the NACA0012 collectors is made to showcase the automatic mesh refinement around the collectors where the steeper velocity gradients occur. Notice how both meshes have similar number of points and however refine different regions more adapted to the problem to solve, thus resulting in faster and lighter simulations, showcasing the advantage of automatic mesh refinement.

Figure E2: Mesh used in the case of the two NACA0012 collectors for the 0th (25) order fluid problem computations it contains 54252 points and forms a number of 106970 triangles, with a close up of the refinement around one of the NACA0012 collectors.

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